

BORON FIBRES

TENSILE STRENGTH, FRACTURE NUCLEATION AND MATERIAL PARAMETERS

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The fracture properties of boron fibres have been investigated in tensile testing. The fracture surfaces were studied in scanning electron microscopy, and classified with respect to the type of defect, triggering the crack nucleation. Histograms of number of failures versus tensile strength interval were made, and showed the relative effects of the different defects.

Formation mechanisms for two types of defects - radial cracks and so-called proximate voids - are worked out and discussed.

Transverse fracture is studied in terms of Griffith's theorem. It is found that proximate voids may act as Griffith cracks and initiate fracture under an axial external load.

The effect of observed residual stresses on axial fracture is investigated. It is concluded that proximate voids can act as Griffith cracks also during axial fracture, and contribute to the formation of radial cracks.

Finally, numerical values of some material parameters are derived from the experimental results.

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Introduction

In the chase for materials of extreme mechanical properties, high modulus of elasticity Y and high fracture stress σ_f are of primary interest. However, for an increasing sector of applications, a low density ρ is an additional requirement, and therefore the specific modulus Y/ρ and the specific strength σ_f/ρ are new material parameters of interest for optimizing mechanical properties with respect to weight and complete system economy. Still a parameter of importance, particularly for the aerospace industry, is a good high temperature strength, a property which is generally correlated to a high melting point T_m .

Approximate numerical values of these properties are given in Table I for a typical carbon steel, tungsten, elementary boron and for boron-tungsten fibres - so-called boron fibres.

Table I

	Y ($\text{kN}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$)	σ_f ($\text{kN}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$)	ρ ($10^3\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	Y/ρ ($\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)	σ_f/ρ ($\text{MJ}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$)	T_m ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Carbon steel	210	4.2	7.8	27	0.54	1350
W	350	3.9	19.3	18	0.20	3370
B	440	13	2.3	200	6	2300
B W fibre	400	4	2.6	170	1.5	2040

It is seen that boron and also boron fibres compare extremely favourably as to specific properties. Arguments of this type are true also for some other light materials and fibres, such as graphite and silicon carbide, and have guided the choice of fibre material for reinforcing purposes.

The present contribution reports some research work on the mechanical properties, particularly fracture properties, of boron fibres. The project does not explicitly aim at composites, but is a study of basic properties of the boron fibre as such.

Production and Fibre Morphology

Boron fibres are manufactured by the following process. A tungsten wire, about $10\ \mu\text{m}$ in diameter, is resistively heated to about $1200\ ^{\circ}\text{C}$ in a reaction chamber. Elementary boron is condensed on the wire surface by chemical vapour deposition (CVD) from a gas mixture of boron trichloride and hydrogen. Deposited boron diffuses into the substrate, which recrystallizes to a mixture of tungsten borides (WB , W_2B_5 , WB_4). In addition, a mantle of boron grows radially to a diameter of about $100\ \mu\text{m}$ (see Figure 1). Thus, strictly speaking, the boron fibre is a composite in itself, made up of a boron mantle, surrounding a tungsten boride core.

A typical feature of the mantle morphology is its nodular structure. From the very first stages of nucleation, the boron deposition is heterogeneous, forming small, individual nodules on the tungsten wire substrate. The density increases until the whole wire surface is covered by radially growing nodules. The nodular morphology of the completed fibre is revealed only by the surface topography, while the interior, as seen for instance from a fracture surface, is quite homogenous.

Fig. 1

Scanning electron micrograph of mantle and fracture surface of a boron fibre. Note the nodular topography of the mantle surface. (The core appears bright because of the higher secondary electron yield of tungsten.)

Fig. 2

Schematic residual stress pattern in a transverse plane of a boron fibre.

Residual Stresses

The diffusion of boron into the core during the mantle growth causes an expansion of the original wire-substrate, which results in the formation of residual stresses - compressive in the core and dilational in the surrounding mantle. At the end of the manufacturing process, the completed, continuous fibre is pulled out of the reaction chamber through a mercury seal. The resulting quenching implies an additional compressive residual stress in the outermost part of the mantle. The final stress pattern is schematically shown in Figure 2, together with representative experimental stress values (1-3).

Mechanical Properties

The elastic modulus of the mantle and the core materials are different. Therefore, minor modifications of the modulus of the complete fibre can be achieved by changing the core-mantle diameter ratio. In practice, however, the elastic modulus can be considered as a material characteristic, essentially impossible to control.

The fracture strength, on the contrary, is known to vary by as much as an order of magnitude, depending on type and site of the crack nucleation.

Experimental

A great number of tensile tests were performed in a Lorentzen & Wettres (ALWETRON) micro-tensile testing machine, with a constant strain rate of $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The test specimens were 50 mm long, with a gauge length of 25 mm. The contact between the grips and the fibre was improved by the use of emery paper. Fibre diameters were measured individually by means of a Mikrokator.

The debris were retained after fracture, washed, given a 200 Å thick gold coating by sputtering, and studied in emissive mode in a JSM-U3 scanning electron microscope (SEM), operated at 20 kV. Several additional specimens of 50 mm length were given an electrolytical coating of nickel. The resulting composite was cut, mechanically polished, ion-etched and studied in transverse and longitudinal sections in a Reichert MeF2 light microscope as well as a JEM 200 B scanning transmission electron microscope, operated in emissive mode at 200 kV.

Correlation between Fracture Stress and Crack Nucleation

The fracture stress is primarily a material parameter, the measured value of which is expected to vary statistically around a mean value. The present results will prove, however, that the observed variations in σ_f can be statistically correlated to the active mechanism of crack nucleation.

Boron fibres fracture in a brittle manner, very similarly to glass fibres, the fracture surfaces exhibiting "hackle", "mist" and "mirror" zones (4,5). The crack nucleation site can generally be traced by extrapolating the hackle lines back into the mirror zone.

By SEM studies, the fracture surfaces were classified with respect to type and site of the crack nucleation. In qualitative agreement with findings by Layden (4), Line and Henderson (2) and Wawner (1), it was found possible to relate the fracture stress σ_f to the following fracture triggering fibre features or defects, which will be described in detail in the next paragraph:

- i) radial cracks
- ii) surface notches
- iii) proximate voids
- iv) fibre core.

Fig. 3 Number of failures versus fracture stress histograms for three types of tested fibres. At the top of the figure, the observed crack nucleation mechanisms are given in relevant stress intervals. R: radial cracks, S: surface notches, PV: proximate voids, C: core interior.

The probability of occurrence for the different types of fracture nucleation is best demonstrated in a histogram over number of failures versus measured fracture stress (see Figure 3). Comparison with the relevant type of crack nucleation for each fracture test shows that it is possible to relate the active nucleation mechanisms to separable stress intervals, as introduced in Figure 3. It can also be seen that, by far, the most severely weakening feature is the radial cracks, which initiate fracture at about one fourth of the stress corresponding to the best fibres.

Crack Nucleation Types

Fibre Core

It is rare that crack nucleation can be traced to a core imperfection. Generally, in the case of core initiated fracture, there is no observable fracture triggering feature. However, the core itself always remains as an intrinsic defect, and the corresponding fracture stress may be regarded as that of a "perfect" fibre.

Fig. 4 Schematic view of a longitudinal section of a fibre.
 a) "Well oriented" nodular growth. The nodule boundary notch angle is α .
 b) "Badly oriented" nodular growth. The nodule boundary notch angle is $\beta < \alpha$.

Surface Notches

It is obvious that the mantle surface nodule boundaries have a more or less pronounced notch effect, implying local stress concentrations in a fibre under external load. An important parameter, in this respect, is the notch angle, i.e. the angle between the nodule tangents at the bottom of a nodule boundary in a longitudinal plane according to fig. 4. The more acute an angle, the higher is the stress concentration, and the more effective is the notch.

Often the quality of boron fibres is judged according to the appearance of the nodular surface structure. So called "well oriented" nodular growth (6) gives a rather smooth surface, with large notch angles (fig. 4a), while "badly oriented" nodular growth gives a corn-cob surface with smaller notch angles (fig. 4b) and consequently a lower nominal fracture stress. The phenomenon has also been referred to as abnormal nodular growth (4,2) and is activated by inclusions or other impurities. It can be suppressed by process cleanliness. There is also experimental evidence (6) that the nodular growth can be efficiently controlled by reaction parameters, such as temperature.

Fig. 5 is a SEM image showing an example of crack nucleation exactly in the bottom of a rather deep nodule boundary. Examples of this type of notch effect were numerous in fibres with badly oriented growth, but were never found in fibres with well oriented growth.

Fig. 5 SEM micrographs of low angle (β) notch initiated fracture ($\sigma_f = 27,8 \times 10^2 \text{ N/mm}^2$). Note that the initiation site coincides with the boundary of the abnormally grown nodule at the arrow.

It is thus concluded that nodule boundaries are active as crack nucleating "surface notches" if the corresponding notch angle is smaller than a critical value. With the manufacturing technique available today, however, this problem is possible to overcome.

Fig. 6 Low magnification SEM micrograph of a fracture surface pair corresponding to a proximate void (at the arrows).

Fig. 7 a) The prismatic surface of the filamentary tungsten substrate.
 b) The filament in a) after a few seconds of CVD of boron (20 kV SEM).

Proximate Voids

Small, fracture triggering pores, immediately outside the core-mantle interface, were first referred to as "proximate voids" by Wawner (1). The morphology has been revealed by studies of fracture surfaces (see Figure 6) and axial sections, and was found to be the following (7). A proximate void (PV) is a prismatic pore in the mantle, with its axis parallel to the fibre axis. The radial extension is of the order of a few micrometers, while the axial extension is considerably longer. Generally, a PV is also somewhat irregularly shaped, with bends and bulges.

The fact that PVs are only found in the innermost part of the mantle, suggests that they are formed already during the fibre manufacturing stage, in the very beginning of the deposition process. Therefore, a special experiment was designed, during which fibres were produced in laboratory equipment, and the deposition process was interrupted after 2 s (8). It was found that the nodules are preferentially nucleated in tight rows along axial ridges in the tungsten wire surface (see Figure 7). The latter are constituted by die marks, originating from the wire drawing process. By this mechanism, parallel boron "prisms" will grow, until eventually adjacent prisms meet and hedge in the interspace.

The situation is shown schematically in a transverse section in Figure 8, from which the radial void height H can be expressed as a function of "groove angle" v , contact angle θ and die mark interdistance X by

$$H = \frac{X}{2} \left\{ \operatorname{tg}v(1 - \cos\theta \sin v) - \cos\theta \cos v \right\} \quad (1)$$

Fig. 8 Surface contact between growing nodules of equal size, nucleated on neighbouring die mark ridges of groove angle v .

An axially elongated void has now been formed, and is essentially protected from access of the reactants and, thus, from further deposition of boron. Subsequent core expansion may change the morphology. A change in volume, however, requires self-diffusion over distances of the order of one nodule diameter, and would involve transport of vacancies from one void to another.

In principle, the radial extension is H , but the cross section has inherited the irregularity of the initial boron prisms, and the void will have more or less sharp bulges. Continued diffusion is, however, expected to have a surface smoothing effect. A drawing of a proximate void, formed by this mechanism, is reproduced in Figure 9.

Fig. 9 Schematic representation of proximate void.

Measurements on SEM micrographs give X values (see Figure 8) between 1 and 2 μm . θ was measured from micrographs of polished cross sections and found to be about 100° . Normally, v is hardly expected to exceed some 20° , which corresponds to a PV height (in μm) $0.25 < H < 0.5$.

Dimensionally, this type of pore is far too small to be identified as a PV from fracture surface micrographs (4,7). Occasionally, however, groove angles of as much as 45° , and even larger, have been observed, which according to equation (1) corresponds to H values of the order of 1 μm . An image example of a void of this size was given in Figure 6. Like all similar examples, it is situated outside a deep groove, of considerably higher groove angle v than the average. The corresponding, observed H values vary in the interval (μm) $1 < H < 3$.

Radial Cracks

Radial cracks can be revealed in etched transverse fibre sections. Examples of optical micrographs are given in Figure 10, which demonstrates the radial extension from within the core to just inside the external mantle surface.

The influence of residual stresses on the path of the radial cracks is quite obvious. A comparison between Figure 2 and 10 shows that the outer crack edge roughly coincides with the outer transition between dilational and compressive stresses. Close inspection of Figure 10 a and b also reveals that in both cases one of the cracks deviates from the radial direction and follows the circular transition region inside the core (at A), while the others are stopped at depths, corresponding to higher compressive stresses.

It was also possible to follow the axial extension of radial cracks in etched axial sections, as demonstrated by Figure 11.

Fig. 10 Optical micrographs of transverse fibre sections, ion-beam etched under slightly different conditions.

Fig. 11 Radial crack in axial section. (20 kV SEM).

Electron micrographs of fracture surface pairs frequently show that the transverse fracture is nucleated at the outer edge of radial cracks (see Figure 12). A typical feature of this kind of fracture is that the transverse crack, when propagating inwards the fibre, follows somewhat different planes on different sides of the radial crack which is also easily seen in Figure 12.

It was also frequently observed that two radial cracks cooperate with one transversely propagating crack, which results in the fracture morphology shown in Figure 13.

Fig. 12 Fracture surface pair exhibiting transverse fracture initiation at the outer edge of a radial crack (see arrows). (SEM)

Fig. 13 Two different transverse fracture surfaces, joined by radial crack surfaces. Note that the latter are of the mirror zone type. (20 kV SEM.)

Because of the pronounced fibre-weakening effect of the radial cracks, it would be of great interest to suppress their formation. Nevertheless, very little has been found about their origin. It has, in fact, not even been clarified whether the formation starts already during the fibre growth process, or later, during handling the manufactured fibre (rolling on spools, preparation of test specimens etc.).

One suggestion is that the dilational residual stress component in the transverse plane might be strong enough to open up a radial crack. The formation as an exclusive consequence of the residual stress situation pictured in Figure 2, would require a critical fracture stress of the order of $0.8 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$, corresponding to the dilational stress peak. Compared to the measured fracture stresses, however, this value is too low to create a crack in a flawless boron mantle. If, however, there are suitable, pre-existing defects, the fracture stress might be reached locally. In the present work, therefore, the situation has been investigated with respect to possible stress concentrators.

Griffith Type Brittle Fracture

In the case of transverse fibre fracture, nucleated at a proximate void, as for example shown in Figure 6, it is of interest to check the possibility that a PV may act as a Griffith crack nucleus.

Further, during the investigation of etched transverse sections (i.e. from non-fractured fibres), PVs were found in radial cracks just outside the core-mantle interface. An image example is given in Figure 14. It is, thus, possible that PVs may act as Griffith cracks also in axial fracture geometry. In that case, they constitute the pre-existing stress concentrators, necessary for triggering the opening up of radial cracks under the influence of residual stresses.

Fig. 14 Proximate void (arrow) in a radial crack, at the core-mantle interface. (200 kV SEM. Ion-beam etched cross-section.)

The Griffith criterion is generally written as a square root relation (9)

$$\sigma_f = \sqrt{\frac{4Y\gamma}{\pi \cdot 2c}} \quad (2)$$

between σ_f and the major axis $2c$ of an elliptical cross-section of a pre-existing void (γ is the surface energy). In the present case, the active void is represented by a PV bulge. It can, in principle, be approximated by an ellipsoid, as schematically shown in Figure 15. A PV in a transverse fracture surface, like that of Figure 16, represents the shadowed, elliptic cross-section in Figure 15, with major and minor axes $2C$ and $2c$ respectively.

Fig. 15 Schematic representation of transverse (shadowed) and axial (dashed) cross-section ellipses of an approximately ellipsoidal proximate void.

Fig. 16 SEM micrograph of PV initiated transverse fracture.

Under the influence of an axial tensile stress, however, the axial cross-section ellipse (dashed in Figure 15) represents the Griffith geometry and has the major axis $2c$ equal to the minor axis of the transverse cross-section ellipse. These particular crack nucleation conditions are typical of the fibre geometry only, and unlike the situation in a plate or slab (10).

A log-log-plot of eq. (2) will be the straight line

$$\ln 2c = q - 2 \ln \sigma_f \quad (3)$$

with direction coefficient -2 and a characteristic intercept constant

$$q = \ln\left(\frac{4Y\gamma}{\pi}\right) \quad (4)$$

In the present work, $2c$ was measured from PVs in SEM images and plotted versus the corresponding σ_f values in a log-log diagram, which is reproduced in Figure 17. The full line represents a least square adjustment of the experimental points to a line, the equation of which is

$$\ln 2c = 8.4 - 2.1 \ln \sigma_f \quad (5)$$

The two dashed lines are drawn so as to include all the points and with the exact Griffith direction coefficient -2 . As can be seen, the agreement with Griffith's law is good. Further evidence of numerical agreement will be given in the next paragraph.

Fig. 17 Logarithmic plot of experimental $2c$ - σ_f points. The values marked x, correspond to Layden (4).

Material Parameters

With the aid of the present combination of simple mechanical testing and microscope analysis, it has been possible to arrive at numerical values of a few material parameters of interest. Corresponding methods for direct measurements are hardly available.

Surface energy

The surface energy γ can be solved from eq. (4) as

$$\gamma = \frac{\pi}{4Y} \cdot e^q \quad (6)$$

Eq. (5) and Figure 17 provide experimental q values. With a literature value $Y = 4.4 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N mm}^{-2}$ (11), the two dashed lines of Figure 17 give a surface energy interval (in $\text{J} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$).

$$2.8 \leq \gamma \leq 6.4 \quad (7)$$

which is of the same order of magnitude as literature values for tungsten (12,13), and also in agreement with theoretical calculations (14).

Critical Residual Stress

Again, apply Griffith's theory on the geometry of Figure 15, but now with the dilational residual stress component σ_θ acting on the PV (cp Figures 2 and 9). The critical void dimension then is the major axis $2C$ of the shadowed ellips in the $r-\theta$ plane. The Griffith criterion is written (15)

$$\sigma_{rc} = \sqrt{\frac{4Y\gamma}{\pi \cdot 2C}} \quad (8)$$

where σ_{rc} represents the critical dilational residual stress necessary for opening up the PV to a radial crack. Unlike the case of constant external load, this crack does not become unstable. During the radial crack propagation, σ_θ is continuously relaxed, and the crack growth proceeds at a low speed, essentially maintaining an equilibrium according to eq. (8), with a decreasing critical stress σ_{rc} matching an increasing crack length $2C$. Consequently, the character of the fracture surfaces remains of the mirror zone type, typical of low speed crack propagation (see Figure 13). Eventually, the crack propagation stops, when the crack fronts reach regions of compressive residual stresses.

Table II. σ_{rc} in $\text{kN} \cdot \text{mm}^{-2}$ for different surface energy γ and Griffith crack length $2C$.

γ ($\text{J} \cdot \text{m}^{-2}$) \diagdown	$2C$ (μm)	1	3
2.8		1.2	0.7
6.4		1.9	1.1

From measurements in micrographs, $2C$ is known to vary between 1 and 3 μm . Table II shows the obtained variation of σ_{rc} , taking also the range of experimental γ values into account.

These values, compared with the experimental residual stress peak of $0.8 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{mm}^{-2}$ (Figure 2), indicate that the mechanism suggested above is numerically possible. In addition, the measurements, referred to by Figure 2, must be expected to underestimate dilational stresses, because the probable presence of already created radial cracks will relax all tangential dilational residual stresses.

Activation Energy for Self-diffusion

The diffusional growth of the fibre core during the production process requires diffusion of boron atoms from the mantle through the core-mantle interface. The self-diffusion of boron in the mantle layer adjacent to the core is equivalent to vacancy migration, directed from the interface. The proximate voids will then act as highly efficient sinks and grow by vacancy absorption. Eventually, a bulge may reach a size which later, during tensile loading, is the critical Griffith size for fracture. Measurements on SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces with crack nucleation at proximate voids therefore yield experimental values of the vacancy diffusion distance x from the core interface to the void. x is related to the activation energy E_D for self-diffusion in boron by Einstein's formula

$$x^2 = 2a^2\nu \cdot t \cdot e^{-E_D/kT} \tag{9}$$

where a is the shortest interatomic distance, ν is the Debye frequency and k is Boltzmann's constant.

Fig. 18 The activation energy E_D for self-diffusion, plotted versus the diffusion distance x , according to eq. (9). The measured interval is introduced in the graph.

E_D can now be solved from (9) for known reaction time t and temperature T . x is, however, uncertain because of the radial extension of the proximate voids. Therefore, a plot $E_D = E_D(x)$ has to be made, as shown in Figure 18, with numerical parameter values, relevant of the present investigation. The possible x values, representing diffusion between the core surface and the two edges of the void, are indicated as the interval (in μm) $1 < x < 3$ between the vertical lines in the diagram. The corresponding activation energy is obtained from the diagram as (in eV) $1.9 < E_D < 2.2$.

In relation to the suggested nucleation immediately at the core, the morphology and extension of proximate voids imply a net outwards vacancy transport over ranges of $3 \mu\text{m}$, i.e. from the core to the outer void edge. Thus in Figure 18, the activation energy for self-diffusion rather corresponds to the longer diffusion path ($\sim 3 \mu\text{m}$), representing the lower energy limit.

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